

The size effect on the drying behavior of castables - An experimental and numerical perspective

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ABSTRACT

Refractory castables present many attractive features. However, for hydraulic bonded monolithics, the major drawback is the long drying stage during its placement due to the likelihood of explosive spalling. The latter is a direct consequence of non-optimal management of the thermal and hygral states that leads to pressurization of water vapor and can induce severe damage to the lining. This phenomenon results in overconservative heating schedules which leads to longer production halts, economic losses and environmental effects. From numerical models to advanced laboratory tests, the missing link between fundamental research and technology innovation relies on the size scale difference among the samples studied in the labs and those lining the refractory equipment. The current study proposes a systematic analysis of the size scale effect by considering conventional thermogravimetry (50mm x 50mm cylindrical samples), macro thermogravimetry (30 cm x 30 cm x 30 cm cubic samples) and also numerical simulations of different heating configuration to unveil likely relationships between different scales and the experiments setups and actual drying process. It was found out some interesting correlation between the mass loss of the macro TGA and the lab one testing a smaller sample size. Further studies to identify and validate the existence of a general scaling law are required, nonetheless, the current study provides a first step towards finally bridging the gap between small laboratory samples and real industrial geometries.

INTRODUCTION

Refractory castable placing is the initial and critical step for the successful operation of high temperature equipment [1]. Due to corrosion, thermal shock and mechanical loads, they can present life cycles that can range from years to even days. For the latter, the substitution of refractory lining can be a bottleneck for the production due to long halts for its maintenance.

In this context, refractory castables can be of great interest as they can be shaped *in-situ*, in complex geometries and the whole process can be automated, reducing their application time [2]. In addition, the composition of such materials can be readily adjusted to optimize specific properties and using additives can lead to distinct behavior which can be suited for specific placing techniques ranging from traditional casting, ramming or even to shotcreting [1,2].

When considering hydraulic bonded castables, usually materials with high density and low permeability, the drying stage becomes the main restriction for faster lining maintenance [1, 3, 4]. Water can be trapped inside the pores and, with the increase of temperature, be pressurized at levels higher than the material's strength. In combination with thermomechanical stresses a violent explosive spalling event might occur, which could completely destroy the equipment's lining or even its own holding structure [3, 4].

Thus, as a countermeasure, overconservative long heat up protocols are often applied for the drying, combined with additives to enhance the permeability of the green material, such as polymeric fibers [1, 3]. With the ongoing efforts to refrain the climate change, safely reducing these heat-up curves is critical for the decrease of refractory castables carbon footprint.

Even though explosive spalling is not restricted to refractory castables, one example being the damage of Portland cement concrete structures under fire [5, 6], the complete understanding of this dangerous phenomenon is still not fully attained.

One example of the aspects that still demands further understanding is the different ways that a material can undergo explosive spalling. Palmer et al. reported the well-known refractory

castable explosion event where large pieces can be thrust over long distances [4], whereas, Jansson et al. described the progressive spalling of reinforced concrete structures [6]. Additionally, the usual thermogravimetry tests under high heating rates display another distinct mode of failure, the complete destruction of the sample in small pieces [1, 3, 4].

These observations highlight that the applied heating rates, the thermal gradients developed inside the material, and ultimately the size of the object being heated affect the explosive spalling behavior. The latter aspect can be related to the so-called "size effect" which implies that the observed strength of a given material can be decreased when considering higher volumes [7]. Besides the original explanation of this effect related to the random distribution of defects which is considered by the established Weibull theory of failure, energetic causes can also be responsible for this behavior [7]. It should also be noted that such size-effects are not only related to the mechanical behavior aspects. Alarcon-Ruiz et al. highlighted that the volume of a sample can be responsible for changes in the measurements of intrinsic permeability of Portland cement concrete [8].

Thus, the objective of current work is to bridge the gap between laboratory analysis and industrial processes by providing insights of the size scale effect on the drying of refractory materials via a complementary combination of experiments and modelling of thermogravimetry tests with samples of different sizes and under distinct heating rates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Analysis

The current analyses were conducted for a high alumina castable containing 5 wt.% of calcium aluminate cement (also referred as 5CAC) and a packing distribution coefficient $q = 0.21$, following Andreasen's particle model. The composition is described in Table 1.

Tab. 1: 5CAC High-alumina refractory castable composition.

Raw Materials		Composition (wt.%)
Tabular Alumina (Almatis)	AT 6-3	18
	AT 3-1	10
	AT 1-0.5	11
	AT 0.6-0.2	9
	AT 0.2-0	16
	AT<45	10
Calcined and reactive alumina	CL370, Almatis	11
	CT3000SG, Almatis	10
Calcium Aluminate Cement	Secar 71, Imerys	5
Distilled Water		5.0
Dispersant	Castement FS60, Basf	0.2

The powders were mixed for 1min and the water content was slowly added along 3 min. Next, the sample was either casted into cylindrical moulds (50mm of diameter and 50mm in height) for the conventional TGA tests, or as a 300mm x 300mm x 300mm cube for the macro TGA analyses (Elkem, Norway). Following the samples were cured for 24h at room temperature inside closed plastic bags with a water containing beaker to keep the environment humid.

Following, the TGA tests were carried out following the description of the experiments shown in Figure 1, with heating rates of 2°C/min, 5°C/min and 20°C/min for the conventional sized samples and 0.667°C/min for the macro TGA. The mass loss curve was obtained by Equation 1, whereas its derivative with respect to the temperature was obtained following the central finite difference approximation described by Equation 2.

$$W(\%) = 100 \times \left(\frac{M_o - M}{M_o - M_f} \right) \quad (1)$$

where M_o is the initial mass, M_f is the mass at the end of the test.

$$\left(\frac{dW}{dT} \right)_i = \frac{W_{i+1} - W_{i-1}}{T_{i+1} - T_{i-1}} \quad (2)$$

where W_{i+1} and T_{i+1} is the mass and temperature at time instant $i+1$, and, W_{i-1} and T_{i-1} are such values at an the earlier moment $i-1$.

Fig. 1: Schematic TGA experiments layout for the (a) conventional sized samples and (b) macro TGA

Numerical Analysis

The simulations were based on the single-phase model proposed by Bažant et al. [5], which is based on two partial derivative equations that describes the balance of mass and thermal energy, Equations 1 and 2.

$$\frac{\partial \rho_{ev}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\kappa}{g} \nabla P_v \right) + \frac{\partial \rho_{deh}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_{ev} is the mass of free (physically adsorbed) water per kilogram of concrete, t is the time, κ is the intrinsic permeability, g is the acceleration of gravity (9.81 m/s²), ρ_{deh} is the mass of chemically adsorbed water released and P_v is the pressure inside the pores, the primary variable of the model.

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \rho C_p = \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla T) - C_l \frac{\kappa}{g} \nabla P_v \cdot \nabla T + \Delta H_{ev} \frac{\partial \rho_{ev}}{\partial t} + \Delta H_{deh} \frac{\partial \rho_{deh}}{\partial t} \quad (4)$$

where T is the temperature, ρ is the density of the refractory castable, C_p is its specific heat, λ is its thermal conductivity, C_l the specific heat of liquid water, ΔH_{ev} and ΔH_{deh} the enthalpy of evaporation and dehydration, respectively, and T the temperature, the primary variable.

For more details on the implementation of the model and its numerical solution, the reader is referenced to Moreira et al. and Cunha et al. [9, 10].

To reproduce the two TGA layouts investigated in this work, the boundary conditions for the tests assume that all sides are free to exchange mass with the environment and for the conventional TGA, the lateral sides of the cylindrical sample are heated by convection and radiation, according to Figure 1, whereas its top and bottom are only heated by convection. Conversely, for the macro TGA, only the bottom of the sample is directly heated, while the other sides are heated by convection. The validation of the model as well as the properties considered can be found in [9, 10].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental results

Figure 2 describes the results of the mass loss comparing the conventional cases with the results by macro TGA, for different heating rates.

Fig. 2: Mass loss comparison of conventional and macro TGA for samples heated under (a) 2°C/min, (b) 5°C/min, and (c) 20°C/min.

It is possible to realize that the mass loss profile for the macro TGA presents three distinct stages. The first one, between 25°C and 130°C, where evaporation of the free water is carried out under a constant rate, the second in the range of 130°C and 290°C, related to the ebullition of the physically adsorbed water, and a last one from 290°C up to the end of the test at 450°C, related to the hydrate decomposition, as described by Luz et al. [1].

The two first stages of the macro TGA drying are better reproduced by the conventional sample heated at 20°C/min. The slower heating rates resulted in mass loss at lower temperatures as seen in Figures 2 (a) and (b). This behavior can be explained by the fact that the higher heating rate applied on the smaller sample compensated the size difference, which proportionally increases the travelled distance that the water moves until it is withdrawn from the body. The third dehydration stage, however, is better reproduced by the sample with the 5°C/min heating rate. As the dehydration reactions are prone to kinetic effects, the different heating rates are known to shift the temperature of the decomposition [1]. Consequently, higher heating rates (20°C/min) are unable to reproduce the decomposition observed in the macro TGA sample, which was heated at 0.66°C/min.

The derivative of the mass loss with respect to the samples' temperature is presented in Figure 3, again for all the heating rates used for the conventional TGA test alongside the result for the macro one.

Fig. 3: Derivative of the mass loss with respect to temperature comparing the conventional and macro TGA samples heated under (a) 2°C/min, (b) 5°C/min, and (c) 20°C/min.

It is possible to observe that for the 20°C/min conventional TGA test, the first peak during the dehydration stage (around 290°C) is convoluted with the initial mass release that occurs on the first two stages of drying (evaporation and ebullition). That it is not detected for the slower heating rates applied to the conventional case, whereas it can be seen for the macro TGA case. In this case, due to the size of the sample and the required time for the heat wave to reach the innermost positions of the sample, the free water removal shows up as a plateau between 180°C and 290°C.

Afterwards, both the macro TGA and the slower heating rates for the conventional cases display a clear peak, that is detected slightly later for the bigger sample. This trend might be related to the slower heating rates which is known to shift the dehydration reactions to higher temperatures [1].

Fig. 4: Temperature difference between the furnace and the sample. The black dashed line is a guideline for equal temperatures (i.e., no temperature gradient between furnace and sample).

Figure 4 shows the thermal gradient between the measured temperature of the furnace and the value at the center of the sample. It is possible to see that the difference is directly proportional to the heating rate and consequently the greatest gradient in the conventionally sized samples is observed for the sample heated at 20°C/min.

Another important aspect that controls the temperature gradient is the thermal inertia of the sample, given by the required energy to heat it by one degree Celsius.

This can be easily calculated by multiplying the samples' density and its specific heat by the sample volume. Assuming the values used for the numerical analysis and neglecting the energy necessary for the water removal, one can deduce that the energy required to increase the temperature of the conventionally sized samples is 9.78kJ, whereas for the macro TGA sample it is 67.71kJ.

This explains why even though the heating rate applied to the macro TGA is the slowest, it has the greatest thermal gradient until the furnace reaches 200°C. After that, the heat wave has already propagated and reached the core of the sample and the thermal gradient of the macro TGA reduces to the smallest one at 450°C.

This specific behavior could also explain why the mass loss results for the macro TGA and its derivative with respect to the temperature is closer to the behavior of the conventional sample heated under 20°C/min up to 290°C.

Other factors that are important such as the surface area available for mass transfer exchange as well as the differences in the heater placements (as seen in Figure 1), and the pressurization observed for each sample could also play an important role in the results observed. Thus, the next section describes the numerical results for the TGA tests.

Numerical results

Figure 5 describes the pressure evolution calculated by the numerical model for the different heating rates and samples size. It is well known, both from real observations and theoretical predictions, that when applying higher heating rates, the pressure levels reached are higher. This can also be observed by the trend in increased pressure peaks for the samples faster heated in the conventional TGA.

Fig. 5: Simulation prediction of the pressure evolution at the centre of the sample as a function of its temperature.

Additionally, the pressure peaks are also displaced for higher temperatures, as at higher heating rates, the water vapor doesn't have enough time to escape the material before the sample attains higher temperatures. This leads to a further pressurization that will increase the velocity of water removal (as can be observed by considering Darcy's law described in Equation 3).

When considering the macro TGA results, it can be seen that even though the heating rate is almost three-fold lower than the slowest conventional heating rate applied, the maximum pressure observed at the innermost position of the sample is eleven-fold higher. This highlights how both the sample's size and the heating rate applied have a direct impact on the drying behavior. For higher heating rates, the water doesn't have enough time to escape before the pressurization event, leading to more intense peaks. Similarly, if

the sample's size is larger, water is still trapped at the innermost positions leading to the greater pressurization.

Thus, for the free water removal (evaporation and ebullition stages up to 300°C), the pressurization observed for the conventional sample heated at 20°C/min and the macro TGA case are closer, justifying the similar trend observed in Figure 2 (c).

To better understand the role of the pressurization and thermal gradients, Figure 6 presents the distribution of temperature and pressure at the moment of the pressurization for each simulated case. Fig. 6: Temperature and pressure distribution prediction at the

moment of pressurization for conventional TGA (a) 2°C/min, (b) 5°C/min, and (c) 20°C/min and (d) macro TGA 0.66°C/min.

The thermal gradient between the center of sample and its surface increases for the higher heating rates and size, changing from 5°C for the conventional sized sample heated at 2°C/min, to 100°C for the macro TGA sample. This highlights that the thermal gradient difference is the key point to be observed for the initial stages of drying of samples with distinct sizes.

Finally, when considering the pressurization region, it can be seen that the heating rate didn't change its position. For the macro TGA however, due to the heating from the bottom (see Figure 1), the pressurization is moving towards the top of the sample along with the heating front.

CONCLUSIONS

The drying of refractory castables is a challenging subject and its understanding is crucial for increasing this process efficiency. Without proper knowledge, the advantages of new compositions designs, additives for drying and even heating methods, will always have a lesser impact due to overconservative protocols that are adopted due to lack of deeper understanding of the process.

In this work, the size effect of samples studied by TGA was considered for samples heated with different heating rates, considering both, experiments and numerical computations.

Firstly, it was possible to identify that for the initial drying stages, the conventional sized sample with the highest heating rate (20°C/min) was the one that closest matched the behavior of the macro TGA heated at 0.66°C/min. By considering the numerical results, it was confirmed that this trend was due to the higher pressurization occurring inside such samples due to either higher heating rates (for the conventional sample), or larger size (for the macro TGA sample).

Due to the kinetics of the dehydration reaction, the behavior of the larger samples was dominated by the heating rate, and thus, the results were closer to the slowest conventional TGA tests at 2°C/min and specially to that at 5°C/min.

Finally, this work highlights the importance of the thermal gradient applied to the sample, and how assuring that similar thermal states are achieved can be the bridging link between laboratory tests and the industrial process optimization. Nevertheless, further studies are still required to unveil likely general laws that might correlate the laboratory and industrial size scales.

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